

Evaluation of Hematological Parameters in COVID-19 Patients**Pankti Soni¹, Parth Navinkumar Patel², Snehal Radadiya³**¹Senior Resident, Department of Pathology, GMERS Medical College and Hospital, Himmatnagar, Gujarat, India²Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, GMERS Medical College and Hospital, Himmatnagar, Gujarat, India³Junior Resident, Department of Pathology, GMERS Medical College and Hospital, Himmatnagar, Gujarat, India

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Abstract:**Introduction:** COVID-19, caused by SARS-CoV-2, has led to significant mortality globally and is associated with various hematological abnormalities. This study evaluates the neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) and platelet-to-lymphocyte ratio (PLR) as predictive factors for critical illness in COVID-19 patients.**Methods:** 500 COVID-19 patients admitted to R. D. Gardi Medical College, Ujjain, from 2020 to 2022 were analyzed. Inclusion criteria involved adults aged over 18 with confirmed COVID-19 via RT-PCR. Exclusion criteria included recent blood transfusions and pre-existing hematological disorders. Hematological parameters were assessed upon admission.**Results:** Significant differences in hematological parameters were noted among patients categorized by disease severity. Key findings included elevated NLR and decreased hemoglobin levels in severe cases compared to mild and moderate cases ($p < 0.001$). PLR did not show significant variation across severity levels ($p = 0.879$).**Conclusions:** NLR appears to be a valuable predictive marker for disease severity in COVID-19 patients, while PLR may not provide additional prognostic information. Further studies are needed to confirm these findings and explore their clinical implications.**Keywords:** COVID-19, SARS-CoV-2, Hematological Parameters, Neutrophil-to Lymphocyte Ratio (NLR), Platelet-to-Lymphocyte Ratio (PLR).This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19), the highly contagious viral illness caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), has had a catastrophic effect on the world's demographics resulting in more than 6 million deaths worldwide as of March 2022, emerging as the most consequential global health crisis since the era of the influenza pandemic of 1918 [1]. After the first cases of this predominantly respiratory viral illness were first reported in Wuhan, Hubei Province, China, in late December 2019, SARS-CoV-2 rapidly disseminated across the world in a short span of time, compelling the World Health Organization (WHO) to declare it as a global pandemic on March 11, 2020 [2]. Since being declared a global pandemic, COVID-19 has ravaged many countries worldwide and has overwhelmed many healthcare systems. The pandemic has also resulted in the loss of livelihoods due to prolonged shutdowns, which have had a rippling effect on the global economy. Like other RNA viruses, SARS-CoV-2, while

adapting to their new human hosts, is prone to genetic evolution with the development of mutations over time, resulting in mutant variants that may have different characteristics than its ancestral strains. It is normal for viruses to change and evolve as they spread between people over time. When these changes become significantly different from the original virus, they are known as "variants". To identify variants, scientists map the genetic material of viruses (known as sequencing) and then look for differences between them to see if they have changed. With the emergence of multiple variants, the CDC and the WHO have independently established a classification system for distinguishing the emerging variants of SARS-CoV-2 into variants of concern (VOCs) and variants of interest (VOIs). Several variants of SARS-CoV-2 have been described during the course of this pandemic, among which only a few are considered variants of concern (VOCs) by the WHO, given their impact on global public health [2]. Since the SARS-CoV-2 virus, the virus that

causes COVID-19, has been spreading globally, variants have emerged and been identified in many countries around the world. Based on the recent epidemiological update by the WHO, as of December 11, 2021, five SARS-CoV-2 VOCs have been identified since the beginning of the pandemic [3]. COVID-19 plays a critical role in the host immune response in disease pathogenesis and clinical manifestation. It triggers the antiviral immune system to produce an uncontrolled inflammatory response that may lead to cause hematological abnormalities such as lymphopenia and abnormalities in granulocytes, lymphocytes and monocytes [4]. The study aims to screen the most useful predictive factor for critical illness caused by COVID-19 such as the neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) and platelet-to-lymphocyte ratio (PLR) which are easily accessible and have been known to correlate with inflammation and prognosis in several conditions.

Material and Method

Hematological details of 500 patients of COVID-19 admitted in R. D. Gardi Medical College, Ujjain over a period of two year from 2020 to 2022 were enrolled in the analysis.

Inclusion Criteria: All patients with the age group of >18 years who had COVID-19 disease confirmed by RT-PCR admitted in R. D. Gardi Medical College, Ujjain during the study period of two years.

Exclusion Criteria: Recently blood transfused patients, previous history of disease primarily affecting RBCs, WBCs, Platelets, Pregnancy. On admission and with the proper consent once

obtained by the patients, detailed history and their outcome were recorded from the case sheet of the patient in the proforma. Patients were categorized on the basis of their clinical features into non-severe who had upper respiratory tract infection and severe cases with lower respiratory tract infection. Blood samples for hematology analysis were collected in EDTA vial and ensured to be at least 02ml in quantity was sent to laboratory for complete hemogram that was done on automated hematology analyzer SYSMEX550-L. Parameters like Haemoglobin, Red blood cell counts, Total leucocyte counts, Differential leucocyte counts, Absolute counts& Platelets were recorded. The data collected was then transferred to Microsoft excel sheet. NLR, MLR, PLR and SII was calculated and entered in the data sheet. Neutrophil: Lymphocyte ratio (NLR) was calculated by dividing the absolute count for neutrophils by the absolute lymphocytes. Monocyte: Lymphocyte ratio (MLR) was obtained by dividing absolute monocyte count by absolute lymphocyte count. Platelet: Lymphocyte ratio (PLR) was calculated by dividing the platelet counts by absolute lymphocyte count Systemic inflammatory index (SII) was calculated as a product of neutrophil count and platelet count divided by lymphocyte count $\{(neutrophils \times Platelets)/lymphocytes\}$.

Results

The mean age of the cases was 54.67 ± 15.51 years with median age 56 year. The patient's age ranged between 18 years and 96 years. While majority of cases 221(44.2%) were in 41-60 years age group, 181(36.2%) patients were of 60 years age [Table 1].

Table 1: Age distribution of the cases

Age Groups	Frequency N = 500	Percent (%)
<=20 Years	8	1.6
21 - 40 Years	90	18.0
41 - 60 Years	221	44.2
>60 Years	181	36.2

Table 2: Gender distribution of the cases

Gender	Frequency N = 500	Percent (%)
Male	319	63.8
Female	181	36.2
Total	500	100.0

Male predominance was seen in 319 out of 500 COVID-19 patients [Table 2].

Table 3: Descriptive values of hematological parameters among COVID- 19 cases (N=500)

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD
Hb (gm/dl)	2.40	17.00	10.11	3.02
TLC (10^3 /ul)	1.44	37.51	12.72	5.51
Neutrophil (%)	44.70	98.30	84.72	10.14
Neutro absolute count (10^3 /ul)	1.21	36.01	10.96	5.29
Lymphocyte (%)	0.50	53.30	10.74	8.51

Lympho absolute count (10 ³ /ul)	0.04	6.41	1.22	0.93
NLR	0.84	193.40	16.24	17.70
Monocyte (%)	0.00	13.00	3.01	2.20
Monocyte absolute count(10 ³ /ul)	0.00	2.63	0.36	0.30
MLR (%)	0.00	5.40	0.45	0.50
Eosinophil (%)	0.00	5.40	0.91	1.18
Platelets(10 ³ /ul)	12.00	641.00	247.45	110.68
PLR	6.50	8840.91	369.07	529.37
SII	44.12	75232.60	3925.59	5600.35

Mean Hb level was found 10.11±3.02 with range (2.40 to 17.0), mean TLC level was found 12.72±6.51 with range (1.44 to 37.51), mean neutrophil level 84.72±10.14 with range (44.70 to 98.30), mean neutrophil absolute count 10.96±5.29 with range (0.50 to 53.3).

Mean lymphocyte count 10.74±8.51 with range (0.5 to 53.3), mean lymphocyte absolute count 1.22±0.93 with range (0.04 to 6.41), mean NLR

16.24±17.70 with range (0.84 to 193.4), mean monocyte 3.01±2.20 with range (0 to 13), mean monocyte absolute count 0.36±0.30 with range (0 to 2.63), mean MLR 0.45±0.50 with range (0 to 5.4), mean eosinophil count 0.91±1.18 with range (0 to 5.40), mean platelets count 247.45± 110.68 with range (12 to 641), mean PLR 369±529 with range (6.50 to 8840) and mean SII 3294.26 ±5316.8 with range (44.12 to 75232.6).

Table 4: Descriptive values of hematological parameters according to severity of disease

	Severity						P value
	Mild		Moderate		Severe		
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Hb (g/dl)	12.93	2.08	9.34	2.61	7.76	1.75	0.000
TLC (10 ³ /ul)	9.38	3.13	12.74	5.00	17.71	5.77	0.000
Neutrophil (%)	79.95	12.43	85.51	8.44	89.96	6.48	0.000
Neutrophil absolute count	7.64	3.08	10.94	4.57	16.04	5.62	0.000
Lymphocyte (%)	14.55	10.86	10.26	6.81	6.19	5.17	0.000
Lympho absolute count	1.24	0.88	1.28	1.01	1.02	0.77	0.058
NLR	12.35	18.96	14.65	13.70	26.10	20.90	0.000
Monocyte (%)	3.57	2.26	2.83	2.17	2.63	2.05	0.001
Monocyte absolute count(10 ³ /ul)	0.31	0.20	0.36	0.31	0.46	0.39	0.001
MLR	0.41	0.52	0.40	0.45	0.63	0.56	0.000
Eosinophil (%)	1.16	1.38	0.80	1.11	0.79	0.97	0.008
Platelets (10 ³ /ul)	245.33	109.72	258.41	110.84	223.37	108.79	0.07
PLR	385.07	767.03	357.67	396.54	373.30	355.56	0.879
SII	3100.40	6580.43	3551.22	3823.76	6103.82	7047.50	0.000

Mean values of TLC (p-value 0.000), neutrophil (p-value 0.000), neutrophil absolute count (p-value 0.000), lymphocyte (0.000), NLR (p-value 0.000), monocyte count (p-value 0.001), monocyte absolute count (p-value 0.001), eosinophil count (p-value 0.008) and SII (p-value 0.000) were significantly increased in patients with severe disease as compared to the patients with mild and moderate. Mean values of Hb (p-value 0.000) was significantly decreased in patients with severe disease as compared to the patients with mild and moderate. Mean values of platelets (p-value 0.07) and PLR (p-value 0.879) was not significantly differ in patients with severe disease as compared to the patients with mild and moderate.

Discussion

The study was conducted on cases of COVID- 19, in the department of Pathology, R.D. Gardi Medical College, Ujjain. In our study, 500 COVID-

19 cases were evaluated during study period. Present study mean age of the cases was 54.67±15.51 years, median age 56year, minimum age 18 year and maximum age was 96 year, majority of cases 221 (44.2%) were belonging in 41-60 years age group, 181(36.2%) in more than 60 years age group, 90(18.0%) in 21-40 years age group and 8 (1.6%) cases were belonging in less than 20 years age group. Out of 500 cases, 319 (63.8%) cases were males and 181(36.2%) were females. Similar results were seen in other studies also, Swati Sharma et al. [5] revealed that, most of patients were in sixth and seventh decades with mean age of 51.12 years. Percentage distribution of patients according to age group was found as <20 year (0.7%), 21-40 (22.7%), 41-60 year (36%), 61-80 year (34.7%),>80 year (6%). Female patients (37.3%) were lesser than males (62.7). Sudhir Bhandari et al. [6] showed that mean age of the cases was 50.40 years. Percentage distribution of

patients according to age groups was <20 years 5%, 20-40 years 23.75%, 40-60 year 40%, >60 year 31.25%. Females' patients (41%) were lesser than male patients (59%) were. Diallo et al. [7] showed that median age in this series was 59 years with extremes ranging from 20 to 90 years. There was a male predominance 65% and female 35%. In our study Out of 500 cases 100(20.0%) cases had severe disease, 249 (49.8%) had moderate disease and 151 (30.2%) had mild disease. Swati Sharma et al. [5] revealed that, 58% of sample population had grade 3 severity followed by moderate severity in 27.3% patients, and grade 1 severity was present in only 14.7% patients. Neema Agarwal et al. [8] revealed that out 351 cases, CT severity score was normal in 5.98% of patients, mild in 21.94%, moderate in 41.60%, and severe in 30.48% of patients. Anant Mohan et al. [9] revealed that among the 144 patients, four (2.8%) had severe disease, whereas the remaining 140 (97.2%) had mild-to-moderate disease.

Present study mean Hb level was 12.93 ± 2.08 , 9.34 ± 2.61 and 7.76 ± 1.75 for mild, moderate and severe COVID-19 disease group, respectively. Hence mean Hb level was significantly lower in severe disease group as compare to the patients with mild and moderate disease. In a meta-analysis by Taneri et al. [10] showed haemoglobin levels were found to be significantly lower in patients with severe COVID-19 as opposed to mild to moderate cases. A similar study done by Henry et al. [11] also showed similar results. The results of our study were also concurring with the results of the above-mentioned studies. Although these mechanisms have been proposed wherein the COVID 19 infection itself leads to a state of anemia, these are to be substantiated with further evidence.

In our study mean TLC was 9.38 ± 3.13 , 12.74 ± 5.00 and 17.71 ± 5.77 for mild, moderate and severe COVID-19 disease group, respectively. Hence mean TLC was significantly higher in severe disease group as compare to the patients with mild and moderate disease. Ruta Vekariya et al. [12] revealed that significant increase in the WBCs level was observed in the severe and symptomatic individuals compared to asymptomatic patients, which might be due to inflammatory response, having a significant association with the disease severity. Brandon Michael Henry et al. [13] also found Patients with severe and fatal disease with significantly increased white blood cell (WBC) count.

In our study mean neutrophil count was 79.95 ± 12.43 , 85.51 ± 8.44 and 89.96 ± 6.48 for mild, moderate and severe COVID-19 disease group, respectively. Hence mean neutrophil count was significantly higher in severe disease group as compare to the patients with mild and moderate

disease. Mean neutrophil absolute count was 7.64 ± 3.08 , 10.94 ± 4.57 and 16.04 ± 5.62 for mild, moderate and severe COVID-19 disease group, respectively. Hence mean neutrophil absolute count was significantly higher in severe disease group as compare to the patients with mild and moderate disease. Mean lymphocyte was 14.55 ± 1086 , 10.26 ± 6.81 and 6.19 ± 5.17 for mild, moderate and severe COVID-19 disease group, respectively. Hence, mean lymphocyte was significantly lower in severe disease group as compare to the patients with mild and moderate disease. In our study mean monocyte was 3.57 ± 2.26 , 2.83 ± 2.17 and 2.63 ± 2.05 for mild, moderate and severe COVID-19 disease group, respectively. Hence, mean monocyte was significantly lower in severe disease group as compare to the patients with mild and moderate disease. Henry BM et al. [13] observed increased neutrophils and decrease in the lymphocytes, monocytes in severe and symptomatic patients compared to asymptomatic patients. Anurag A [14] showed that similar findings in this study. Also, Yang et.al. [15] and Abdul Wariset. al. [16] found similar results.

In our study mean NLR was 12.35 ± 18.96 , 14.65 ± 13.70 and 26.10 ± 20.90 for mild, moderate and severe COVID-19 disease group, respectively. Hence mean NLR was significantly higher in severe disease group as compare to the patients with mild and moderate disease, similar findings also found in Aditya Anurag et. Al. [14], Abdul Waris et. al. [16], SadiaTaj et. [17] and Liu J et. Al. [18].

In our study mean MLR was 0.41 ± 0.52 , 0.40 ± 0.45 and 0.63 ± 0.56 for mild, moderate and severe COVID-19 disease group, respectively. Hence, mean MLR was significantly higher in severe disease group as compare to the patients with mild and moderate disease. Yang et.al. [15] and Abdul Wariset. al. [16] found MLR ratio was significantly increased with severity of disease. Decreased MLR ratio is as an indicator of poor prognosis so increased chances of mortality among patients suffering from COVID-19. Ruta Vekariya et al. [12] revealed that MLR ratio did not show significant difference between 3 groups.

In our study mean platelets was 245.33 ± 109.72 , 258.41 ± 110 and 223 ± 108 for mild, moderate and severe COVID-19 disease group, respectively. Hence, mean platelets were significantly lower in severe disease group as compare to the patients with mild and moderate disease. Ruta Vekariya et al. [12] study did not find changes of platelet count with the severity of disease. Similar findings were found in Sadia Taj et. [17] Study while yang et.al. [15] and Abdul Waris et.al. [16] Found significant thrombocytopenia is associated with significantly ill patients of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19). Platelet could be a suitable biomarker for

recognition of coagulopathy and its severity. In our study mean PLR was 385 ± 767 , 357 ± 396 and 373 ± 355 for mild, moderate and severe COVID-19 disease group, respectively. Hence, mean PLR was significantly not differed in severe disease group as compare to the patients with mild and moderate disease. While Ruta Vekariya et al. [12] found PLR ratio increased in severe patients compared to symptomatic and asymptomatic patients, this findings support by previous study of Daniel et. al. [19], Abdul Waris et. Al. [16] and Yang et.al. [15] PLR ratio determining the severity of COVID-19 disease.

In our study mean SII was 3100 ± 6580 , 3551 ± 3823 and 6103 ± 7047 for mild, moderate and severe COVID-19 disease group, respectively. Hence, mean SII was significantly higher in severe disease group as compare to the patients with mild and moderate disease. SII remained a reliable predictor in most of the conducted studies on COVID-19 so far. Usul et al. [20] found its superior predictive ability than NLR and PLR in COVID-19 diagnosis, as its values were significantly different in SARS-CoV-2-positive and -negative individuals. The proposed SII for helping in the COVID-19 diagnosis was 479.1. Xue et al.[21] studied the relationship between several markers and disease severity. They found that SII could significantly predict disease severity in the univariate but not the multivariate analysis, but still better than several markers, such as NLR.

Conclusion

The present study is aimed evolution of haematological parameters among COVID-19 cases and categories the cases in three group's mild, moderate and severe disease. We concluded that TLC, Neutrophil, NLR, PLR and SII values were found to have statistically significant positive correlation with COVID-19 severity. Blood investigations like Lymphocyte and Monocyte count have statistically significant correlation with COVID-19 severity. No significant correlation was observed between PLR and COVID-19 severity. Hence, parameters like Hb, TLC, NLR, platelets, MLR and SII are important to predict about the severity of disease.

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